

Security Sector Reform in Africa: How does the success of Security sector reform reinforces peace building and stability in the reconstruction processes of post-war African states. Case study of Sierra Leone and Liberia.

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List of Abbreviations

AFRC - Armed Forces Revolutionary Council

AI - Amnesty International

APC - All People's Congress

AFL - Armed Forces of Liberia

AU - African Union

CPA – Comprehensive Peace agreement

DDRR – disarmament, demobilization, rehabilitation and reintegration

DFID – Department for International Development

DPKO - UN Department of Peacekeeping Operations

Ecomog – ECOWAS Cease-fire Monitoring Group

ESF - ECOWAS Standby Force

ECOWAS – Economic Community of West African States

ERU – Emergency Response Unit

GOL – Government of Liberia ICG – International Crisis Group

GSU - General Services Unit

ICGL – Interim Contact Group on Liberia

IMF – International Monetary Fund

LNP – Liberia National Police

LURD – Liberians United for Reconciliation and Democracy

LFF - Liberian Frontier Force

MODEL – Movement for Democracy in Liberia

NPFL – National Patriotic Front of Liberia

NSS – National Security Strategy

OECD DAC – Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development Assistance Committee

PAE – Pacific Architects and Engineers

PMC – Private Military Company

SL-MOD - Sierra Leone Ministry of Defense

SLPP - Sierra Leone People's Party

STTT - Short-term Training Teams

SLA - Army of Sierra Leone

SLP - Sierra Leone Police

SSR – Security Sector Reform

UK – United Kingdom

UNAMISL - United Nations Mission in Sierra Leone

UNDP – United Nations Development Program

UNMIL – United Nations Mission in Liberia

UNPOL – United Nations Police

UNSC – United Nations Security Council

USAID – United States Agency for International Development

USA – United States of America

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DEDICATION

This research dissertation is dedicated to my dear beloved parents Sworo Alfred Sekwat and Yangi Grace Zaharia, my generous and helpful Uncle Alakai Joseph Sekwat who was shouldering with Education from Secondary level and up to date and not forgetting Uncle Emmanuel Tunda Sekwat. My special dedication to my beloved wife Muja Joyce for the patience, love, inspiration, prayers and support she gave me during my studies and my children Juru Aromeo Sworo, Kadi Aromeo Sworo, Poni Aromeo Sworo, and Yobu Aromeo Sworo. My beloved brother Wuni Moses Sworo, Losuk Francis Sworo and my younger brother Loding Sworo. My dedication also goes my sisters Pita Hariet Sworo, and Jomburu Scovia Sworo.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1.1. BACKGROUND TO THE PROBLEM

The end of the cold war, signify coalitions of countries, international organizations, Non-governmental organizations and donor states pursued and engaged in intervention policies under the context of post-conflict reconstruction and peacebuilding especially for countries recovering from a protracted violent war which resulted in state failure (Smith- Höhn, 2010:1). Since the introduction of peacebuilding as an essential aspect of intervention in post-conflict countries by the then UN Secretary-General Boutros Boutros-Ghali, the concept has become an important element of successful preventive diplomacy, peacekeeping, and peace-making. (Hänggi, 2004:1) Noted that Security sector reform emerged as a concept that was broadly accepted by security experts, development practitioners and democracy advocates as a crucial component in the post-war reconstruction processes that gained prominence in international discourses. And especially within the international donor community ranging from the World Bank, United Nations, and individual donor countries, thus, it is viewed as an important part of State-building and reconstruction processes in the Post-Conflict countries (Cawthra, 2009:19; Brzoska, 2003, Keane and Bryden, 2008).

The familiar concept of the reforming security structure had come to the limelight since the public domain speech by Clare Short, the then British Minister for International Development in the year 1998 (Brzoska, 2003:3; Ball, 2010:29). From the ideal point of view, security structure is operated and managed in a way, which aligned to norms of democracy, and good governance. Emerging SSR literature has been aiming in addressing changes in the security sector actor's effectiveness and efficiency and the need to establish their role in a democratic

governance framework. The given security structure would be said to be well functioning owing to its association with the concepts of democracy and good governance (McCartney et al., 2004).

1.2. PROBLEM of STATEMENT

Sierra Leone and Liberia both share similarities as countries that were both established as settlements for freed slaves and post-conflict states that emerged from violent in the West Africa Mano River Basin. The Liberian civil war started in 1989 and eventually spread to Sierra Leone in 1991. Both countries had protracted violent war were external peace negotiation was broken later and following the international led peace agreements, the Britain's Department for International Development (DFID) and Ministry of Defence (MOD) and the U.S because the two countries respectively maintain some close ties with Britain and USA State Department devoted effort and resources in reforming the security sector of both Sierra Leone. The security forces of the two countries characterized by lack of discipline, unprofessionalism, low morale, rampant corruption, soldiers were badly trained, and poorly equipped as well as undesirable civil–military relations. And their security forces played an unenthusiastic role during the two civil wars as they were accused of committed mass atrocities. Therefore, this thesis evaluated how the success of Security sector reform reinforce peace building and stability in the reconstruction processes of post-war African states. Case study Sierra Leone and Libera.

This research used the term 'Success' thoughtfully about 'SSR success.' The thesis used the word, but it does not indicate overall achievement of the total holistic goal of SSR, rather, an indication of the significant and sustained recovery of the security conditions of the referred case studies contrasted to the prior conditions. Henceforth, the important cases of SSR success

with improved security system may still have crime related issues at high levels, political suppression, or human security related threats.

1.3. Methodology

The primary objective of this thesis was to examine how the success of Security sector reform reinforce peace building and stability in the state building and reconstruction processes of post-war African countries. Thus, any SSR in post conflict societies data was considered necessary and vital. The research was qualitative, hugely relying on analysis of descriptive data. This thesis used secondary literature sources of data mainly from scholarly articles, books, journals and publications from think-tanks who deal with SSR, official documents such as Comprehensive Peace Agreement. And the researcher used the archival or traditional library as particular data collection method.

To evaluate how the success of Security sector reform this thesis selected the Sierra Leone and Liberia as the two post-conflict societies. And multi-method comparative case study research designed was used to track the progress made by respective countries in reforming their security sector achievements. The study designed was comparative and case-oriented because to analyse the success of Security sector reform in the reconstruction processes of post-conflict societies, a range of factors were taken into consideration to inform the empirical analysis of the data. Hence such an approach was necessary. The research questions for this thesis requires an in-depth analysis of SSR in the post-conflict societies context as well it necessitates the amount of universal validity. In this case, the comparative approach is very much suitable for comparison across cases allows a clear understanding of each instance. And the case study designed method take into consideration of the individual historical context.

The research in a careful examination of SSR as a sustainable peace building and state stability approach measure in the reconstruction processes of post-war states with a keen interest in Sierra Leone and Liberian. The thesis uses the four overarching SSR objectives as yardstick for empirical assessment of the success and failure of SSR in this case study and these includes;

1. Establishment of effective governance, accountability and oversight structures in the security system;
2. Improved the delivery of security and justice services.
3. Sustainability of fairness and security service delivery

1.4. OBJECTIVES

The primary purpose of this thesis is to examine how the success of Security sector reform reinforce peacebuilding stability in the state building and reconstruction processes of post-war African countries. The Sierra Leone and Liberian security defense system was not only dysfunctional during the war period, but also characterized by a lack of discipline, unprofessionalism, low morale, rampant corruption, soldiers were badly trained, and poorly equipped as well as undesirable civil–military relations. However, SSR pieces of literature argued that Sierra Leone and Liberian adopted SSR program improved the army and professional police development through training that equipped the security sector capacity to respond to any national security threat. The case study crises and the implementation of the SSR program invoked the researcher to evaluate how the effectiveness and the success of Security sector reform reinforce peace building and stability in the reconstruction processes of post-war African. In championing of the primary objective, the following sub-objectives have been selected.

- Examine the SSR historical perspective in Sierra Leone and Liberia
- Study the comparative success of SSR in Sierra Leone and Liberia.
- Discuss the contribution of the International Community in the post-war African countries Sierra Leone and Liberian SSR.

1.5. Significance and rationale of the study

This research study would be of enormous significance to academia, policy makers and researchers, and post-conflict states that are dealing reconstruction programs. The thesis would contribute to the existing literature on the SSR program in African notably Sierra Leone and Liberia. Hence, the research would seal the gap between the studies on the prospects of how the success of Security sector reform reinforces peace building and stability in the reconstruction processes of post-war African states. Case study Sierra Leone and Liberia.

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CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction

This section of the literature review scholarly articles, surveys books, and any other sources relevant to the subject of Security Sector Reform, theory or area of research. The section provides a summary, description, and critical evaluation of these works of literature.

2.2. General concept of Security Sector Reform

The security sector reform point of departure is that, although it emerged in the 1990s as a concept, it remained contested and lacked a notable accepted definition. Nonetheless, according to (Aboagye and Rupiya, 2005:252), the definition of security sector reform refers to “the equipment of defense within the state effectively and efficiently and within the framework of civilian democratic control”. Whereas, Albrecht and Andersen, (2010:1) noted that the SSR definition put forward by the Development Assistance Committee (DAC) of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD DAC) is the one widely accepted by scholars and practitioners. Hence, “Security sector reform means transforming the security sector/system, ‘which includes all the actors, their roles, responsibilities, and actions. And working together to manage and operate the system in a practice that is more consistent with democratic models and sound policies of good governance, and thus contributes to a well-functioning security framework’” OECD-DAC (2005: 20).

And according to (Valasek, 2008:1), Different several actors in the SSR embraced both broader or narrower meaning of SSR while the diversity of words is in most cases used interchangeably; security sector reform, security sector transformation, security sector modernization, and many other terms. However, Valasek believed there is some level of convergence towards the definition of SSR by the Development Assistance Committee of the Organisation for Economic

Cooperation and Development (OECD DAC). Therefore, SSR tends to address both vacuum in security sector or the multitude of security providers something which is unlike Cold War era. contemporary SSR is not just measured by the capacity of Security forces, but how well they are managed, monitored, and held accountable, more than merely training & equipping, linked to democratization. Development of both institutions capable of providing security and efficient civilian oversight mechanisms, prioritize installation of (robust) state structures/systems.

Wulf (2004:339) emphasized that SSR overall objective to commit to ensuring an environment that is secure and conducive for a civil population to participate in development activities. The primary focus of international actors in supporting countries emerging from conflict is in achieving overarching four objectives. 1) Establishment of accountability, effective governance and oversight architecture in the security sector; 2) Development of local ownership and leadership of the Security Sector reform process. 3) Improved the efficiency of safety and justice services delivery; 4) Ensure Sustainability in the provision of security and justice services.

However, (Egnell and Halden, 2009:29) questioned the overarching objectives of SSR as to whether the goals were not too ambitious. And these SSR aims include; “democratization, good governance, gender equality, civilian oversight of the armed forces, transparency and accountability.” Egnell and Halden, (2009:29) emphasized that there is a question whether SSR, as articulated in its objectives, will indeed build a state from violent conflict to be democratic, transparency and accountability while keeping its political stability in the long run.

(Wulf, 2004:5; Anderlini and Conaway, 2004:32) Argued that the Security sector reform initiatives address four broad areas as it is a complicated process which involves the civil

society, several government ministerial agencies. Henceforth, a comprehensive SSR encompass four dimensions aiming to achieve a democratic, affordable, accountable and civilian-led security structure. These dimensions include Political, Economic, institutional, and Social aspects. The political dimension is democratic, and civilian control over the security sector bodies, the economic dimension point concern with the security forces allocation of resources which requires the participation of the legislature and other government agencies in determining the rational allocation of financial, human and types of equipment for the security department. And the SSR Institutional dimensions is concerned with the transformation of physical and technical structures of different security sector forces and institutions to meet democratic principles. While the societal aspects concern with the guarantee of the citizen's security being internal or external.

According to (Schnabel and Born, 2011:8), the conventional wisdom detects that the concept of normative theory of security sector reform assumes that countries are far better off with protection division which promotes economic development, peace, and security. And a system that based on the norms of democracy, good governance, and it supports a security sector which is effective, efficient and accountable to its citizens (Schnabel and Born, 2011:8). And Smith-Höhn, (2010:2) emphasized that there is an acknowledgment of the fact that there can be no whatever aspect of development without peace and security. And this has made international development organizations, donor countries and practitioners to draw a huge focused on reconstruction efforts towards reforming the security sector of post-war countries even though there some scholars who don't agree with the concept. Henceforth, this thesis is going to investigate about how does the success of Security sector reform reinforce peace building and stability in the state building and reconstruction processes of post-war African countries.

2.3. Sierra Leone SSR

Gbla, (2006:82) asserted that the Armed Forces of Sierra Leone (AFRSL) in the 1990's was characteristic by a lack of discipline, unprofessionalism, low morale, rampant corruption, soldiers were badly trained, and poorly equipped as well as undesirable civil–military relations. And this made Sierra Leone adopt SSR as national reform program way back to March 1996 after the country had experienced and continued to experience violent conflict and state collapse. While (Onoma, 2014:145) noted that the Lome' Agreement articulated the restructuring and reform of the Armed Forces through the SSR agenda. The program aimed to rebuild new national armed force that is exclusively loyal to the state of Sierra Leone, and these soldiers ought to be willing to carry out their constitutional mandate. The reform and restructuring program was to rebuild professionalism in the Armed Forces of Sierra Leone which is accountable to the civilians, respect human rights, have transparent financial management procedures, and have the sense of democratic values.

(Malan et al., 2003:89-90) Noted the United Kingdom gave a generous support to reform the Sierra Leone Armed Forces that was carried out by DFID. The program aimed at equipping, training and advising Sierra Leone government forces. The SSR reform agenda through the support of the United Kingdom helped the establishment of high Ministry of Defence in Sierra Leonean with the ability to; ‘‘formulate, implement, monitor and evaluate the Republic Sierra Leone Armed Forces strategic defense policy for effectiveness and fostered within a democratic governance framework.’’ Gbla, (2006:84).

Both (Albrecht, 2010:14; Gbla, 2006:81) asserted the that the UK also gave support to overhaul the Sierra Leone armed forces that had executed two coups in the 1990s. Similarly, there was a massive help for the reform and restructuring of the police forces to re-establish the SLP. And

(Ginifer, 2006:802) emphasized that the police reform and restructuring program managed to put oversight mechanisms in places like the highest police body that have got the power to provide civilian oversight of policing in Sierra Leone and the police council. Hence, government regulators enable the efficient discharged of responsibilities in the security sector in a transparent, accountable and democratic manner.

Albrecht, (2010:69) argued that the Sierra Leone SSR program paid maxima attention to improving the robust, vigorous and efficient judiciary system. The Sierra Leone government and the UK DFID-fund co-operated to the Law Reform Programme which aimed to; improve the ability, capacity and working effectiveness of the judiciary, including higher courts and local courts applying customary law. Reform of the legal code to better reflect contemporary needs and the presentation of this redrafted legislation to Parliament through the Ministry of Justice; and Training of all levels of legal personnel, including High Court judges.

2.4. Liberian SSR Post-Conflict Reconstruction

According to (Ebo, 2005:16), Liberian had been in a violent conflict for 14 years, and following the brutal war, a Comprehensive Peace Agreement (CPA) later signed in August 2003 Accra Ghana that which gave a chance for reconstruction of the state institutions. Ebo, (2005:14) asserted that the Liberian security sector primary source of the dysfunctionality was because the armed and all security forces had only functioned in the interest of the regime other than acting for the benefit of the public. Thus, Ansorge, (2011:270) argued that the only way to success and sustainability of Peace in Liberia post-conflict reconstruction largely depend on the security sector reform that could function efficiently, ideally within a framework of effective democratic control.

Harrison-Cudjoe, (2012:62) argued that SSR initiated in both governments of Charles Taylor and Ellen Johnson Sirleaf. The only difference was that Taylor resisted the role of ECOWAS oversight of the security reforms even though the SSR mandated by the Abuja II agreement rather his restructuring was in a partisan manner that enables the proliferation of multiple parallel military structures. But the 2004 SSR under Ellen Johnson Sirleaf mandated by the August 2003 Accra Ghana Comprehensive Peace Agreement which stipulated for the restructuring the Liberian Armed Forces and requested the government of United States to play a leading role in the reform process.

Bryden and Chappuis, (2015:77) argued that Liberia SSR program played a significant role in putting effort to rebuild the Liberian army, trained new Liberian National Police, which now can protect and secure its national frontiers, and Liberian civilians. And these are the great success of SSR in the peacebuilding and stability. Although Bryden and Chappuis acknowledge the failure of SSR being locally owned, lack consistency legal framework, the Liberia civil society voices remain limited, and the executive has power at the expense of the Judiciary.

Ebo, (2005:30) emphasized that although the guns are silent but not absent from the hands of Liberians signifying that the absence of guns is necessary but does not grantee peace. Warning that there will be a great danger of setback in the process of the reconstruction if improvement of the SSR rebuilding process not strengthened. The Liberia post-conflict SSR lack a comprehensive framework for implementing the security sector reform activity; the Liberia SSR put much focus on police reform at the expense of other security institutions and democratic oversight. And the civil society has a limited voice in the reconstruction of the security sector in Liberia, hence these factors Liberia peacebuilding and stability.

2.5. Critical view of SSR in post-conflict countries

Scholars such as (McCartney and Wils, 2004:9; Wulf, 2004:2) Offer a convincing argument that the concept of the Security sector reform happens to be not such an old notion in the thought of post-conflict peacebuilding, state transformation, and development, but it has evolved into an increasingly popular approach to address some of the challenges experienced in transitional societies in the post-conflict scenario. While aspects of state building after a war, such as addressing the issues of good governance, democracy, transparency, and accountability, transforming the society peacefully, ensuring human security and diminishing poverty programs have been part of whole security architecture. Therefore, any effort to reform any state's security is linked to those factors as well (Wulf, 2004).

The popular concept of the reforming security structure had come to the limelight since the public domain speech by Clare Short, the then British Minister for International Development in the year 1998 (Brzoska, 2003:3; Ball, 2010:29). From the ideal point of view, security structure is operated and managed in a way, which aligned to norms of democracy, and good governance. Emerging SSR literature has been aiming in addressing changes in the security sector actor's effectiveness and efficiency and the need to establish their role in a democratic governance framework. The given security structure would be said to be well functioning owing to its association with the concepts of democracy and good governance (McCartney et al., 2004).

Brzoska and Heinemann-Grüder, (2004:121) argued that Societies which emerged from brutal conflict and military interventions have prompted international community, international organizations, and coalitions of countries to frequently engage in the process of post-conflict state building and reconstruction in the aftermath of the war. And the agenda of the Security

Sector Reform is one of the essential elements of the post-conflict reconstruction process. The rebuilding of the security sector concerns with the restoration of the formal government security institutions to re-establish legitimate state monopoly of violence.

2.6. Role of international community in SSR in post-conflicts reconstruction states

According to (Sedra, 2010), SSR is a donor assistance policy that which is a prerequisite for state stability and sustainable development especially for countries emerging from conflict or making transitions from authoritarianism, fragility or failed states. SSR is much more than the training of armed force and police based on the idea of building a Weberian state, where it is the monopoly use of coercive means, rather how well these troops are monitored, managed and held accountable in a democratic manner. Therefore, the security sector reform process involves the disassembling of the players and structures that were responsible for the state failure as result of their violent armed acts. Secondly, it requires the rebuilding of the security architecture institutions, structures and processes which prove for a secure environment conducive promotes human development, helps to reduce poverty, good governance, based on democratic principles and the rule of law.

As a role and contribution of donor countries, Yebleh, (2016:59) asserted that the UN's SSR program under the auspices of UNMIL in collaboration with the Liberia government worked hard to realize gains in the SSR program and prevent any resurgence of conflict. While in Sierra Leone, (Pickering, 2009:30) argued that Sierra Leone post-war period witnessed the implementation of a large-scale reconstruction assistance programs, ranging from immediate emergency aid, medium and to long-term peacebuilding and state-building objectives by the United Kingdom. The SSR program was funded through the UK's Africa Conflict Prevention Pool (ACPP). The Funding and coordination mechanism established to promote cooperation

strategy to conflict-related assistance between DFID, the MoD, and the FCO. Operations funded by the ACPD covered disarmament, demobilization, and reintegration (DDR), help to reform the security sector, while some support goes to the UN-sponsored Special Court for Sierra Leone, and the Truth, and Reconciliation Commission.

McCartney et al., (2004:5) argued that United Nations Development Program (UNDP) argument on “Human Security” is that it is one of the important concepts of security. Henceforth, matters of internal conflicts and violent wars signify the failure of state ability as a monopoly of violence in providing her citizens with security and stability. In the presence of a situation characterized by social disorder, security threats, and violent conflicts limit peace and development. Consequently, policy makers, donor community, international organizations and scholars focusing on post-war reconstruction processes and state building thought that to support nation building processes and to prevail over violent conflict, it was essential to focus on security sector reform.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.2.1. Peacebuilding

The aftermath of the Westphalia peace treaty led to the development of institutional global and state formation process which was under the control of international order concept and just order for social demands. The post-cold war era of peacebuilding, peace-making and humanitarian intervention followed suit of the Westphalia peace treaty concept of the state as a monopoly of violence. Informed kinds of literature on the consolidation of peace and peace-making had been positive or normative which focuses mostly on problem-solving in the context of 'How to build or fix the peaceful state.' State-building is the concern with the stipulation of the state with its technical, bureaucratic infrastructure and security. However, peace building shapes public institutions, norms, and laws towards the normative principle of 'good state.' The argument is that failed and weak states have greater implications for regional security and conflict prevention. Thus, the aim of state building and liberal peacebuilding is to build a framework that runs against the predatory aspects of state formation

Lambourne, (2000:3) defined post-conflict peace consolidation in the perspective of post-conflict as “strategies designed to promote a secure and stable lasting peace in which the core human needs of the population are met, and violent conflicts do not recur.” This definition incorporates the concept of both negative peace and positive peace. Negative peace means (absence of physical violence) while real peace means (absence of structural violence). Peacebuilding is concerned with meeting needs of the society. The idea is about the need for security and order, recognition of identity, a reasonable civil standard of living, and worth of everyone in the society.

According to (Ricigliano, 2003:447), Peacebuilding intervention is being categorized into three types, and these include; political, social, and structural.

Political peacebuilding intervention category which is (formal peace processes, peace-making, personal efforts to support lawful peace operations). Fundamentally Political peacebuilding focuses on reaching agreements between warring leaders or their organizations for example between governments side, and rebel movements. It is also concerned with the matters regarding declaring a ceasefire, resolving a dispute, and finally reaching an agreement.

The social peacebuilding intervention deal with initiatives that are involved transforming issues that undermined the smooth link between the warring parties in the conflict. It also focuses to address the kind of perceptions and attitudes that undermine peace, for instance, initiating programs of truth and reconciliation commissions that can bring in the healing of inter-ethnic wounds and acknowledgment of the past mistakes. Social peacebuilding aims to break down inter-ethnic stereotypes.

The structural peacebuilding initiative intention is to strengthen the available assets which enable a peaceful society to be built while taking into consideration the needs of the civilian population within the community. And this category of peace building mainly focuses on the reconstruction of institutions or systems which promote sustainable functioning peacefully societies. For example, good governance, security sector reform, the rule of law, among others.

The international community is facing a grave challenge civil violent conflict which is either intrastate wars or triable clashes in the post-Cold War. Thus, the way in which how the global can respond to such conflicts became a concern to both policymakers, scholars, and students of international relationships and conflict management. Therefore, post conflict peacebuilding was invented as an operation tool for mitigating or prevention of violence from reigniting after

the initial termination of hostilities like ceasefire (Paris, 1997:54). The then UN Secretary-General Boutros Boutros-Ghali introduced the concept of peacebuilding in *An Agenda for Peace*. As time pass by, the concept not only applies to rebuilding in post conflict communities rather it also includes conflict management, conflict prevention, and post-conflict reconstruction activities.

Therefore, in the due processes of using the peacebuilding theory to examine the success of SSR, this thesis discussed the importance of SSR in ensuring lasting peace and stability in the post-conflict peace building process. Comprehensive SSR help to aid deconstruction of violent through restructuring and reforming of security apparatus that deals with the provision of security institutions like the police, military, intelligence, prison personnel, including reforming the judicial court system. Hence, the rebuilding of the security architecture institutions, structures and processes enable a secure environment conducive to promotes human development, helps to reduce poverty, promote good governance based on democratic principles and the rule of law.

2.2.2. Concept of Post-Conflict societies

The post-cold war period witness increased intensity shift in the way wars are wage; it became more of civil war, intrastate other than interstate which made peace-building and reconstruction of post-conflict and war-torn societies have become central to international relations and international agencies. As an intervention policy of multilateral international development and bilateral agencies in delivering programs of humanitarian and emergency response, the additional effort made to address the post-conflict transitions and socioeconomic rehabilitation by these development organizations. The post-conflict reconstruction and peacebuilding program have targeted three areas in state building: 1) re-establishing and reform security

sector, 2) reconstituting legitimacy of the state, and (3) rebuilding effectiveness of service delivery to the civil population. The ‘war on terrorism’ has added more implication to the peacebuilding and reconstruction of post-conflict agenda. Failing and failed states are considered as safe havens for terrorists to carry out their operations that endanger not only the lives of citizens of the Failing and failed states rather global citizens are in threats, thus greater need for tackling the post-conflict evolutions and socio-economic rehabilitation. Therefore, the post-conflict peace-building agenda of intervention have gone beyond the purpose of humanitarian and development, but it has encompassed the idea of national and global security (Brinkerhoff, 2005:3).

The term Post-conflict is being used interchangeably with terms such as post-conflict recovery, post-conflict reconstruction, and post-conflict peacebuilding. Although there is lack of consensus in both academia and policy-making on the definition of a post-conflict situation, this thesis defines post-conflict societies as; Those communities that had recently experienced armed conflict. While seldom those conflicts are international, in more recent history, those battles tend to be domestic and civil. Post-war nations face a myriad of challenges in different forms. The success of countries in wrestling with these problems affects the post-conflict well-being of the country and the potential of the country to relapse into war. While the issues that any one society faces are unique to its situation, history, culture, and conflict.

According to Smith-Höhn, (2010:13) definition of post-conflict societies, as those societies where an agreed cessation of the intra-state violent conflict reached, although, the international community’s recognition of the government side as legitimate. ‘post-conflict society’ further can be defined as a community that has risen from protracted violent war either through international military intervention, externally brokered peace negotiations or overwhelming

success of either warring faction over another. However, Smith-Höhn, (2010:13) argued that definitions only imply that a post-conflict period characterized by peace a phenomenon which does not describe violent conflict adequately. Consequently, Smith-Höhn believed that post-conflict period is often marked by violence as well during times of war, there is a circumstance where there is no violence.

Sierra Leone and Liberia represent some of the few countries under the context post conflict reconstruction/rebuilding since the end of the Cold War. These two nations had the feature of a protracted violent conflict and associated with the destruction of lives, property and the state, society, and economy. Sierra Leone and Liberia as post-war states offer an honest chance to prove the viability of comprehensive security sector reform and reconstruction.

2.2.3. Human security

Human security emerged in the era of the post-Cold war, and it was United Nations Development Program that first popularised in the 1990s. The concept was acting as a link between various Humanitarian, social and Economic matters with an objective to lessen human suffering while assuring their security. McDonald, (2002:279) argued that the greatest challenge in analysing the concept of Human Security is that there is no clear agreed conventional consensus as what the definition of Human Security is, and what the concept seeks to do?

Although the meaning of human security remains contested, Tadjbakhsh and Chenoy, (2007) asserted that there is some level of consensus among the concept advocates and promoters who believed that Human Security is a shift from a state security centred to people-centred security approach. The Human Development Report in 1994, defined Human security in two aspects; 'Security from chronic threats like disease, hunger, and repression' and 'protection from

harmful and sudden disruptions in daily human life.' However, Newman, (2010:78) understanding of Human Security in the broader term as 'freedom from want' and 'freedom from fear.' And the UNDP noted that the categories of potential threats to Human Security are; Economic, Health, Food, Environment, community, personal and political security (Paris, 2001:90).

Table one: Types of Human Security Threats.

Type of Security	Examples of Main Threats
Health security	Deadly infectious diseases, unsafe food, malnutrition, lack of access to basic health care
Economic security	Persistent poverty, unemployment
Personal security	Physical violence, crime, terrorism, domestic violence, child Labor
Environmental security	Environmental degradation, resource depletion, natural disasters, pollution
Food security	Hunger, famine
Community security	Inter-ethnic, religious and other identity based tensions
Political security	Political repression, human rights abuses

The tradition Westphalia concept of security which was state-centric approach understood as national security with the ability to defend the state against external threats has been redefined to incorporate the broader notion of human security with a key focus on individuals' protection. McDonald, (2002:279) asserted that some defenders of human security Scholars argue that much of the security threats for many people in the world perhaps even most come from internal civil conflicts, environmental, disease, criminal violence, hunger, and contamination. While for others, their state may be the greatest threat, other than from an 'external' enemy. Human security thus seeks to question beliefs and institutions that give privilege to 'high politics' above individual occurrences of loss and insecurity. The fact that Human Security acknowledges the security of people, it does not mean that human security is certainly in conflict with state security; the country in ideal circumstances remains the central principle provider of security.

2.2.4. Security and Security sector reform in the post-conflict reconstruction perspective

The concept of SSR since its evolution in the Post-Cold war era has gained a prominent relevance to the rebuilding of the security sector of those countries that emerged from the violent civil war, interstate wars, military intervention. SSR fits in the perspective of post-conflict reconstruction of failed states. Development and peacekeepers actors in the rebuilding processes view SSR as an essential element to the success of post-conflict reconstruction. Thus, SSR is a central feature of the international intervention that constructs the wider approach to conflict prevention, peacebuilding and post-conflict reconstruction sweep from short-term goals of humanitarian relief and rehabilitation to long-term development goals like reforming justice and Security Sector reform.

2.2.5. Defining the Security and security sector

After the end of the cold war, the view toward security profoundly changed because the concept has steadily deepened and widened no longer as before where security is perceived to be state and military centrist criticised. Thus, leading to the broadening of the security in a wider manner which included non-military threats that have leverage over the cause of violent conflicts. And the range of such threats includes; civil wars, transnational crime, resource conflicts, and migrations. These threats are perhaps as some result of natural disasters, diseases, poverty, environmental decline, and resource scarcity which affects not only the state but individual, community and international security (Anderson, 2012:34). Because of the proliferation of civil wars, failing states, the international community recognised that it is better to protect individual and groups rather than dysfunctional states. The safety that led to new security concept of 'human security' and 'societal security' to emerge. Which is concerned about freedom from fear and liberty from wants "community security, political security, food security, economic security, health security, environmental security and personal safety" Hänggi, (2004:2). In the context of international security, there is an acceptance that the world is interdependence politically, economically and socially, hence, there is a need to cooperate for global and international security interest Johansson. Consequently, in the perceptive of security enrichment in a broader context, the practices to improve safety, to stimulate development and to build peace have become interconnected and interdependent. Thus, it has led to the establishment of 'Smart Power' in context it is an amalgamation of hard and soft power a strategic integration of Defence, Development, and Diplomacy, (Wilson III, 2008).

2.2.6. Security sector

Much as the concept of security remain contested, Hänggi, (2004:2) argued that the security sector definition has many as the definition of the number of the concept scholars and international players in trying what exactly comprises of 'security sector.' Nonetheless, at a certain point, there is some level of convergence regarding the general understanding of 'security sector' shaped by the scope of the adopted perspective.

Aboagye and Rupiya, (2005:252) the definition of security sector reform refers to “the provision of security within the state effectively and efficiently and within the framework of civilian democratic control.”

Wulf, (2004:399) asserted the SSR defined by the OECD/DAC which emphasises that the security sector has many sub-sectors that need to be reform. No doubt, by far the armed forces have the largest portion of the security sector. While other core security sector actor's sub-sectors for reform include the police, paramilitary forces, gendarmeries, presidential guards, customs and immigration, coast guards, border guards, reserves intelligence services, and the judiciary. Wulf, (2004:339) further noted that SSR is the transformation of the security system which comprises of all security actors, their actions, responsibilities, and roles to ensure that the operation of the security system is managed in an accountable manner. That embraces democratic values and good governance principles because the primary objective of SSR is to enable a secure and peaceful environment conducive to development.

Smith-Höhn, (2010:22) stressed that often time scholars and practitioners while defining SSR had cited the guidelines of OECD DAC on security system reform and governance and these guidelines includes;

1. The Core security actors which consist of armed forces, paramilitary Forces, police, gendarmeries, presidential guards, intelligence security services, local security units, coast guards, border guards, customs authorities, and reserve.

2. Security management oversight bodies consist of the executive, national security, legislature and select legislative committees, ministries of defense, internal organisations (finance ministries, financial audit, budget offices, and planning units) and civil society organisations.

3. Justice and law enforcement institutions: judiciary, justice departments, prisons, criminal investigation and prosecution services, human rights commissions and ombudsmen, customary and traditional justice systems.

4 The Non-statutory armed security, include the guerrilla armies, political party militias, private bodyguards, private security companies.

According to (OECD, 2005: 20), “Security system reform is a term used to explain the transformation of the security order that includes all the actors, responsibilities, their roles, and actions. Working together to control and operate the sector in a practice that is more compatible with democratic standards and sound beliefs of good governance, and thus contributes to a well-functioning security structure’.

In the adoption of a broad definition of the security sector, a valuable distinction between the security perspective and the governance perspective is worth mentioning in embracing the more general definition of the sector.

From the security perspective, the sector reflects the more comprehensive security view as it includes both statutory and non-statutory security forces. The state security institutions vested with the formal mandate in the delivery of public safety, being internal or external violent or

coercion are the military, police, the intelligence and secret services, gendarmerie and paramilitary forces, border and customs guards, justice and penal institutions. While the sector encompasses of private and other no statutory security actors such as liberation armies, security companies, non-state paramilitary organisations, guerrilla among others. Therefore, security sector from the security perspective definition encompasses of statutory and non-statutory security forces

From a governance perspective, the security sector includes public sector players responsible for managing and controlling state security apparatus in control of the monopoly of violence such as the executive government, defence and of the interior ministries, the parliament and the judiciary. To embrace the democratic and good governance principles like any other public sector the non-statutory civil society should play, an important role in security sector governance and oversight management. (Smith-Höhn, 2010:22; Hänggi, 2004:4).

Table two: Definitions of the ‘Security Sector’

Perspective	Definition A	Definition B	Definition C	Definition D	Focus
Narrow	Security forces	Groups with mandate to wield instruments of violent	Core security actors	Organisations to authorised to use force	State centric
	Civilian management and oversight	Institutions to with a duty to managing	Security management and oversight	Civilian management and oversight bodies	

	bodies	and monitoring	bodies		
Broader		Judiciary, penal system, human rights	Justice and law enforcement institutions	Justice and law enforcement institutions	Human Centric
			Non- statutory security forces	Non-statutory security forces	
				Non-statutory civil society groups	

Source: Hänggi, (2004:4)

Smith-Höhn (2010:4) concluded while summing the definition of security sector as evolving and debatable but there is a tendency of widening the scope of the sector beyond the state-centric concept because of the new security threats resulting from the post-Cold war era, post-9/11 and the war on terror. Besides, the thought of non-statutory, private security and civil society actors as parts of the security sector.

CHAPTER THREE

POST-CONFLICT RECONSTRUCTION IN AFRICA.

3.1 INTRODUCTION

After the end of the Cold-war, some commentators predicted that the global south or third world countries had a chance to surge towards democracy, peace, and development as the bit super-power rivalry had ended. However, Africa kept being merged in civil wars although their wars for independence from the colonial powers was over. The Africa continent in the 1990's saturated in bloodier violent conflict such as in Somalia, Sudan, Sierra Leone, Ethiopia and Eritrea, Rwanda, Burundi, Democratic Republic of Congo, Liberia, Angola to mention but a few. And these conflicts pose significant risks to internal, regional and international security, hence attracted the concern of international community to engage warring parties in committing to peace agreements.

Consequently, these events have encouraged the international community, African Union (AU) and the Regional Economic Communities (RECs) in Africa to invest in the facilitation of negotiations for the interest of peaceful resolution of conflicts while ensuring effective implementation of peace agreements. Therefore, the reconstruction of public institutions of these African countries among others, Sierra Leone, Burundi, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Liberia, the Central African Republic (CAR), Sudan, Somalia and Côte d'Ivoire, become international community top priority. Aboagye and Rupiya, (2005:249).

Ehrhart and Schnabel, (2005:2) argued that Post-conflict reconstruction is not only the aim of terminating the war rather moving a state that emerged from violent conflict to peace by rebuilding the social, political, and economic institutions to be able to meet their internal

livelihood and security challenges. Post-conflict peacebuilding is multidimensional which requires complex approach cutting across political, diplomatic, and economic efforts and it encompasses security, governance, humanitarian relief, economic, psycho-social elements aiming at bringing both negative states of peace in the short run, and positive peace at the run. Henceforth, the United States Institute of Peace, Peacekeeping, and Stability Operations Institute, (2009) emphasized six elements of post-conflict reconstruction as discussed below;

Security sector reform: After any violent conflict, the security system becomes dysfunctional, thus, during the post-conflict peacebuilding a comprehensive security reform is needed to ensure that the state becomes capable of proving safety to its citizens' both from internal and external threats. The success of any post-conflict peacebuilding process, security sector reform is a primary condition. Recovery of the economy, society, and building political institutions requires a secure environment.

Humanitarian Relief: Violent conflict harmfully affects citizens directly and indirectly because it results in deaths, injuries, displacement, and the destruction of the existing infrastructures like road, hospitals, schools, electricity, water supply, and others. And for these reasons, the need for Humanitarian Relief is vital to prevent more human suffering by enabling access to basic needs such as water, sanitation, food, shelter, and health care to survivals.

Infrastructure repair: Rebuilding of Infrastructure is an essential element of Post-Conflict reconstruction because Armed conflict destroys the physical components of modern society, like, railroads, roads, bridges, airports, power supplies, water, and wastewater management system, telecommunications.

Economy Reconstruction is one the essential dimension of Post-conflict reconstruction because the purpose is to consolidate peace and security through achievement of sound and

sustainable socio-economic development after the war. Economy Reconstruction engages in the rebuilding of infrastructure, giving relief assistance, reforms of the structural macro economy of the state to enable sustainable growth, and create a conducive environment for private sector development.

Post-conflict Governance reconstruction: Most conflicts and collapse of states are because of management breakdown which manifested into humanitarian emergency and reduction of society into a state of nature where life is nasty short and cruel. (Katorobo and Peace, 2005:21). Post-conflict reconstruction of the element of governance is an essential thing to do since a legitimate political government is needed to provide security and policy decisions to diffuse future violent conflict.

Social/Cultural: Regeneration of public institutions like Schools, arts, medical, and religious organisations do help in developing decision-making capacity of public goods. Therefore, rebuilding the affected social groups, social and cultural institutions by the conflict contribute to building confidence in reconciliation efforts among competing groups for the interest of ultimate peace.

3.2 Security Sector Reform in Africa

The African continent has experienced devastating violent conflicts most of which were in the 1980s and 1990s and have ended. Africa war-prone region with hopeless security, economic and social prospects to doom. In the contemporary Africa, there are presently more circumstances of post-conflict than conflict countries. Hence, Post-conflict peacebuilding is multidimensional which exercise which encompasses security, governance, humanitarian relief, economic, psycho-social. And because the circumstances of political, economic and security Changes have compelled most African governments virtually to give a thought to some

degree of reform in the way how security institutions governed, operate, funded, or interact with the civilian constituencies.

In Africa, the concept of Security sector reform (SSR) progressively acknowledged as a fundamental contribution to promoting peace, development, and stability. Thus, Efficient post-conflict peacebuilding requires a comprehensive security sector reform of the society. In this reconstruction program, the process obliges an active involvement of the political, military, and economic actors. Ehrhart and Schnabel, (2005:6) emphasized that the kind of “security sector” which incorporate “all the organisations which have the authority to use or order the use of, force or risk of force, to protect the country and its civil population. Including those public structures that are responsible for their management and oversight”. And the sector involves the military and paramilitary forces, police forces, intelligence services; border guards, judicial and penal systems, and unique civil structures responsible for the security management and oversight.

The concept of the security sector reform instruction aimed at offering an innovative approach to the governance of security sector mostly intended for either failing of failed states or states emerging from violent conflict. The SSR paradigm was perceived by donor’s community and other partners in post-conflict reconstruction process as a necessary precondition for peace and sustainable development. The concept was view at an angle of holistic SS reform approach with a link to development while based on the principles of accountability, legality, and transparency. According to Bryden, (2005:1), African had and has continued to be an international supported SSR arena programs based on the focus on the post-conflict peace building. Even though the concept received international and some African states backing and welcomed the idea, some countries viewed it with skittish because of the suspicion that SSR

resonates the developed or western countries imposition their values, approach and methods in the execution of public policy program.

Bendix and Stanley, (2008:13) argued that several African states security regimes have been branded with a collection state actors and non-state actors including among others the, guerrilla armies, local militias, warlords, vigilantes, self-policing community groups. However, the state may just represent one among many of the security providers in the case of fragile or post-conflict countries. Hence, in some circumstance, the state becomes a cause of insecurity to the population while sometimes the non-state actors may be viewed as a better provider of security to the community. Due to many post-conflicts cases in Africa, SSR became compelling resulted in various international interventions through the SSR program which is a prominent element of post-conflict reconstruction. Bryden, (2005:1) asserted that the international engagement in Africa SSR had presented a big worry about intervention and local ownership.

Africa has a tremendous experience and knowledge that has overwhelming contributed to the SSR evolution because the SSR discourse development has indebted so much to Africa expertise and practical experience. There had been varied lessons learned from the Africa transitional treats which have injected underlying meanings to the SSR mainstream discourse. The South Africa Experience has informed the SSR discourse with the term like Security Sector Transformation (SST) because of the former insecurity and injustices caused by the then apartheid government, and this demanded a comprehensive demolishing of the unjust government structures which were in support of the apartheid system. According to Bryden, (2005:3), The nature of the South Africa Security Sector Transformation (SST) emphasized a fundamental shift in security provision and planning.

3.3 The role and contribution of donors and international community in the post-war reconstruction African countries.

The security Sector Reform program incorporates many actor and players ranging from international players, donor's countries, regional actors to local actors. Thus, SSR tended to be development donor-dominated approach, and multi-agency in character in nature and donors have often used different words such as post-conflict reconstruction, poverty-reduction programs, public expenditure reform or some combination of the three. Often time, the role of donors and the international community has been limited to funding and aiding disarmament, demobilization, rehabilitation, and reintegration (DDRR). Which in most cases typically coordinated by the UN Mission in various countries on the peace-building and post-conflict reconstruction programs on one hand or the UNDP and the World Bank on the development on another hand.

Hutchful and Fayemi, (2005:82) argued that direct donor engagement with SSR as such is still comparatively rare. The few current examples involve DFID, which has exercised leadership in the development of SSR as a concept, in Sierra Leone and now Uganda and, increasingly, Ghana, and conceivably the role of the UNDP in the elaboration of the Malian Code of Conduct. "Traditional" reciprocal relations in the military arena continue to thrive as is the case, for example, with excellent links maintained by the US through IMET and other programs. Sufficient of the focuses is on the peacekeeping training (RECAMP, ACRI, BMATT). Britain through DFID has also known for her involvement in police reform in several SADC countries. For example, in South Africa, there was thorough donor engagement at several levels in the police reform process. Britain was also involved in military integration and retraining in South Africa, Zimbabwe, and now Sierra Leone (through the IMATT program).

According to Yebleh, (2016:59), the UN's SSR program under the auspices of UNMIL in collaboration with the Liberia government and worked hard to realize gains in the SSR program and prevent any resurgence of conflict. Although the UN Security Council resolution specifically resembled at the transformation of the Liberian police and military. The UN (UNMIL) has appropriately played a great role in reforming and equipped the Liberia security sector to prevent a resurgence of violent conflict as well as enduring security issues within Liberia. Observers noted that due to improvement in the safety area by UNMIL, more than 140000 Liberians refugees had returned home. Liberia in 2013, for the first time, could contribute to the UN peacekeeping force, sending 50 military personnel to fulfill peace and security mission in Mali.

The United States government sponsored the reformation of The Liberian army gradually in line with the Liberia CPA. Even though, the US-led strategy to the Liberia security sector reform executed by sub-contracting DynCorp International which is an American private security cooperation. However, in 2010, that contract was replaced, and the US military train and equipped the new Armed Forces of Liberia (AFL). The US army operation enhanced by the Economic Community of West African countries, such as Ghana and Nigeria, who supported the AFL's general staff. The struggles of these actors produced nearly two thousand rigorously trained and vetted Liberian armed forces, with only estimated five percent former soldiers, Yebleh, (2016:39).

The UK's military intervention in Sierra Leone was a turning point in her public commitment as evidenced by her substantial expansion in the extent and scope of its relief program. (DFID 2001:159) Noted that DFID's funding for Sierra Leone tripled from roughly £9 million to £30 million between the year 1999 and 2000. The Sierra Leone post-war period witnessed the

implementation of a large-scale reconstruction assistance programs, ranging from immediate emergency aid, medium and to long-term peacebuilding and state-building objectives. The support was funded through the UK's Africa Conflict Prevention Pool (ACPP). The Funding and coordination mechanism established was to promote cooperation strategy to conflict-related assistance between DFID, the MoD, and the FCO. Operations funded by the ACPP covered disarmament, demobilization, and reintegration (DDR), help to reform the security sector, while some support goes to the UN-sponsored Special Court for Sierra Leone, and the Truth, and Reconciliation Commission (Pickering, 2009:30).

The inability of the Sierra Leone security forces to preserve peace and stability throughout the conflict, and in some circumstances indeed partake in a conspiracy that fuelled insecurity. The security sector reform has sensibly become a fundamental focus for UK assistance as a prerequisite for state stability and reconstruction. In 1999 DfID gave an extensive support to implement a comprehensive SSR in Sierra Leone SLP (Albrecht, 2010:14; Gbla, 2006:81). The UK also provided support to overhaul the Sierra Leone armed forces that had executed two coups in the 1990s. Hence, Pickering, (2009:31) argued that the UK aid to improve the Sierra Leone security sector seems to have helped reduced the likelihood of assaults on civilians by armed forces and deterred the army from seeking to intervene in the political arena again.

3.4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Several African states have performed considerable on the matter of SSR, ranging from a comprehensive SSR Sierra Leone which has a relative success story, real advancement toward democratic civil-security relations (Ghana, South Africa, Benin, Senegal). To other forms of reforms (Cameroon, Togo, Guinea, and lately Kenya) still, have cases where the armed forces are often time deployed blatantly and routinely in contradiction

of their political opponents. SSR scholars believe many post-conflict African countries SSR programs were either international supported with UN missions' operations and donor countries such as Sierra Leone, Namibia, Mozambique, and possibly Liberia among others. And self-implemented SSR with little international support like in South African. African states that had operationalized the SSR principles and had considerable success in implementing the SSR program is regarded to have established a self-sustaining security system in their countries. Thus, successful implementation of SSR through the support of international community and individual donor countries in the post-conflict African countries reinforced the theory of peacebuilding and stability.

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CHAPTER FOUR

SECURITY SECTOR REFORM IN LIBERIA

4.1. Liberia Historical Background

Liberia was established in 1822 as a new home for the slaves freed from America. It maintained the assistance of the U.S. Navy became a colony and finally a member of the Commonwealth and got her independence 1847. Liberia experienced a deadly civil war in 1989 when Charles Taylor and a small group of Libyan-trained rebels launched a rebel movement called National Patriotic Front of Liberia (NPFL). In 1990, ECOWAS negotiated peace agreement (Abuja Accord), however, Peace in Liberia was short lived as Liberians United for Reconciliation and Democracy (LURD) started to wage war in 1999 with the AFL. And in 2003, UN Mission in Liberia (UNMIL) was established followed by post-conflict reconstruction programs such as disarmament, demobilisation, and reintegration and rebuilding and robust Security Sector Reform. (Dennis, 2006).

4.2. Liberia SSR background

According to (Ebo, 2005:16) Liberian had been in a violent conflict for 14 years, and following the brutal war, a Comprehensive Peace Agreement (CPA) later signed in August 2003 Accra Ghana that which gave a chance for reconstruction of the state institutions. The reconstruction and peace process in Liberian followed a pattern of UN modus of events characterised by series of actions including the signing of the peace agreement, peacekeepers deployment, programme of disarmament, demobilisation, and reintegration (DDR), security sector reform and lastly democratic elections. The security system of Liberian fundamentally failed during the war period as there was a failure in effective control of the armed forces by the command. The status quo was lacking good governance of the security sector that led to dysfunction of the

whole system. Thus, the then Liberian security sector not only needed a reform rather a profound transformation to ensure efficient security system that works within the democratic norms.

The Liberian protracted civil wars (1989-96 and 1999-2003) security forces were all engaged in the armed struggle, violated, degraded, abused and denigrated, committed sexual and gender based violence including sexual slavery, rape, forced marriages, and other dehumanising forms of violations. (Ansorge, 2011:270). The success and sustainability of Peace-making and post-conflict reconstruction in Liberia largely depend on the security sector reform that could function efficiently, ideally within a framework of effective democratic control. Therefore, Liberia had undergone two different stages of security reform, first was during Charles Taylor's regime and later during Ellen Johnson-Sirleaf regime under the auspices of UNMIL.

4.3. SSR during Charles Taylor regime

Charles Taylor the warlord-turned-president mode of restructuring the security sector was in a partisan manner that enables the proliferation of multiple parallel military structures was Taylor's divide and rule tactics, to gain and secure loyalty and strengthen personal control. He resisted the efforts of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) to oversee a process of SSR While he marginalised the role of the AFL by setting up parallel bodies such as the Special Security Unit, Strike Force, Alert Force Republican Guard, ATU, Special Operations Division and the Counter Force. Taylor's inclination created parallel organisations. For example, in October 1990 Taylor created the National Patriotic Reconstruction Assembly (NPRA) in acknowledgment to ECOWAS's creation of the Interim Government of National Unity (INGU).

The creation of the many parallel units can probably justify by arguing that it was Taylor's means of ensuring jobs for his former NPFL associates. Who may have become a threat to his government if they remained unemployed Taylor's partisan manner of the reforming of the security sector created a safety hazard that ruined his presidency. Charles Taylor era failed to address pressing priorities as part of the security reform process such as general security system reform, constitutional reform, poverty reduction, economic recovery. And coupled with the weak judicial system, the armed forces behavior so brutal resulted into unnecessary arrest, poor detention conditions, rape, sex slavery among others Malan, (2008:3).

4.4. The armed forces of Liberia

Ebo, (2005:14) argued that the Liberian security sector primary source of the dysfunctionality is that throughout the history of Liberia, the armed and all security forces had only functioned as machinery in the interest of the regime other than acting for the benefit of the public. Therefore, given the broader gap between the government interest and the local population interest, the role of the armed and all security forces had been characterised by repression and oppression. The clear evidence was indicated by the fact that the first security forces the 'home guards' were created to protect the settlers from the Liberian indigenous Communities. By no surprise, the same 'home guards' evolved into the Liberian Frontier Force (LFF) in 1908, and later the same (LFF) transformed into Armed Forces of Liberia (AFL). The LFF was used as apparatus to secure the compliance of the indigenous population, and it keeps promoting the expansionist settler agenda. Henceforth, following Liberia long history of violent conflict, the security system of Liberia essentially failed, and restoration of peace and order demand comprehensive reform of the Liberian Armed forces to enable the sector function efficiently and ideally within a framework of effective democratic control.

The (CPA) Comprehensive Peace Agreement signed in Accra Ghana August 2003 stipulated for the restructuring the Liberian Armed Forces and requested the government of United States to play a leading role in the reform process. And the United States accepted the help demobilised the army, recruit, vet, train, and equip the new army. The mission of the armed forces according to the CPA, “the Mission of the Liberia Armed Forces shall be to defend the national sovereignty and, in extremis, respond to natural disasters.” Malan, (2008:27).

Following the election of Ellen Johnson Sirleaf and inauguration of her administration in 2006 after a deal was negotiated for the departure of Charles Taylor and go into exile in Nigeria. The US government contracted DynCorp International to provide basic facilities and basic training for the AFL and contracted the Rand Corporation to report on the strategic objectives of the reform process. Ellen Johnson Sirleaf formed the Governance Reform Commission (GRC, later the GC), as mandated by the CPA to provide recommendations for the drafting of a new national security policy for Liberia, a tasked eventually released to the public in 2008, Ebo, (2005:27). The SSR Program supported the Liberia MOD in the process of recruiting and vetting of new applicants to the AFL of about 12,100 while DynCorp continued to design and manage the recruiting and vetting program.

(Nilsson and Kovacs, 2013:6) Asserted that the delay to start the recruitment of the new armed forces until January 2006 while more than 100,000 ex-soldiers had been demobilised and disarmed from the ranks and files of the AFL, MODEL, LURD, and ex-GOL, including the rebel forces led to criminal acts. As by mid-June 2005, the troops looted the Liberia’s largest military barrack because of protest in Monrovia because of non-payment of salaries financial constraints. Some critics of the process had labeled the Liberia armed forces reform luck reflection of the comprehensive review of Liberia’s security environment. But the most

important element that this thesis realised as a success of the SSR program in Liberia is the fact since then Liberia has never again slid back to war meaning the SSR is reinforcing peacebuilding and stability.

4.5. Liberian Police reform during Ellen Johnson-Sirleaf regime

The police force reform program is essential to be given a very high priority in such a society like Liberia that had witnessed an extended period of violent conflict, and they were highly politicised, militarised, personalised and centralised during Taylor era. The police sector was used as a mean of keeping Taylor former fighters the NPFL through employment when Taylor took power in 1997. Under Charles Taylor, the Liberian National Police were militarised, and as being former NPFL militias, they used weapons indiscriminately against civilians. Thus, the police reform is a significant aspect of UNMIL's mandate.

Besides the UNMIL's strong mandate by the UN Security Council with mighty chapter vii powers to restore peace and order, rendering provision of advisory remit, broad SSR, DDR and emphasis to restore government legitimacy (Rees, 2008:151). The CPA gave the United Nations Civil Police (UN CivPol) responsibility to reform the Liberian National police during the transition period. The CPA Article VIII 4, 5. Article VIII (1) charged CivPol to train a new police force; "There shall be an immediate restructuring of the National Police Force, Special Security Service (SSS), custom security guards, the Immigration Force, and such other statutory security systems. These restructured security troops shall adopt a professional orientation that emphasises democratic principles and respect for human rights, a nonpartisan approach to duty and the avoidance of corrupt practices". And according to Malan, (2008:48) the UN Security Council Resolution 1509 mandated the UN Police officers (UNPOL) to restructure, retrain, and re-equip the Liberian National police service. And the UNPOL were

required to help the Liberian National Police in maintaining law and order, and this UNPOL started the task since 2004, Rauch and Van Der Spuy, (2006:147).

In July 2004, the National Police Academy reopened, and new police forces taken from both within and outside Liberia National Police. The recruitment was gender sensitive as 15% were women by the UNMIL civilian police. According to Malan, (2008:48), reports indicate that by August 2007, the National Police Academy had graduated a total 3,522 new police officers and deployed across the country. However, the Liberian reform program has been criticised for bringing in many former police men/women who served in the previous governments. Despite the effort inserted to train the police forces, the LNP remains ineffective because of lack of vital police equipment such as radios, vehicles, handcuffs, and raincoats.

Ebo, (2005:21) affirmed that the process of the recruitment was thorough in making sure that the recruits backgrounds investigated as Ebo cited the International Crisis Group confirming recruits vetted and the process was vigorous to ensure the recruits are not criminals. The entire names of the recruits published in the Monrovia newspapers with the intention of requesting the public to report any recruits who had been involved in illegal activities during the protracted war. Every possible effort was inserted within the available resources to verify the new LNP recruits as far as the UNMIL went and established an “integrity bank” to run the background checks of the applicants and the Liberian National Law Enforcement Association used it for screening.

However, Malan, (2008:50) argued that the vetting process was not perfect because the background checks were not adequate as admitted by a member of the U.S. SSR Team in Monrovia. The names of recruits only sent to nongovernment organisations (NGOs), and agencies for backgrounds check and scrutiny other than testing individual applicant with their

communities where they came. Nevertheless, how serious the challenges of policing would be in Liberia, no doubt the situation in Liberia has somehow improve compared to the previous governments that had not attempted to reform their security sector especially the police department.

4.6. Liberia Judicial and legal reform

After the Liberal war ended, there was complete agreement among the Liberian civil population about their distrust toward Liberia's courts of justice and the consistency of the Rule of Law had collapsed. The formal justice sector has become weak, and corrupt resulting into Liberians have had limited faith in judicial systems to preserve their interests or fundamental rights', (Hayner and Centre for Humanitarian Dialogue, 2007:19). Ending impunity and instilling the notion equality before the courts of law is vital to creating stability in the post-conflict state. The agenda of the SSR policy incorporated matters of "transitional justice." Which is a kind of justice instrument that can be employed during the interim period from war to peace specially to deal with a larger number of crimes committed during the violent conflict and the victims to ensure justice delivered so as not to threaten peace and stability OECD-Development Assistance Committee, (2005:10). Thus, Liberia peace building exercises are not an exception to reform efficient, transparent and legitimate judicial institutions, structures and necessary law changes in areas such as legal training, law reform, capacity-building and case management systems. However, the Liberian CPA didn't deal very well with the need to reform the justice sector seriously, although the LURD proposed the establishment of the constitutional review commission, it was objected by the international community citing concerns of resources and the time for the legal review would be limited.

Hayner, P.B., and Centre for Humanitarian Dialogue, (2007:23) cited little progress was made towards reforming the Judicial sector since the CPA effectiveness. The Liberian judiciary system remains dysfunctional, miserable to the extent of contributing to impunity other than fighting it. Problems are related to, lack of qualified personnel, lack of adequate separation of powers, unpaid salaries for prosecutors, judges, and court staff, and limited adherence principles of transparency and accountability, systemic corruption among others. It's been noted that by late 2005, 97% of the inmates in Liberian jails had only held in pretrial detention. Years into the implementation of the CPA, several donor countries were very hesitant to commit resources to the reform of the sector as the transitional government kept indicating little clear political commitment and strategic plan to make improvements necessary.

4.7. The Role of Civil Society Engagement with SSR in Liberia

Ebo, (2005:26) stressed that the civil society is a major player in the security sector democratic governance that act as watchdogs, agents of change, informants of technical input that promote the values of transparency, accountability, and participation in the operationalisation security sector democratic governance. History reveals that Liberia had been having a vocal and active civil society but Taylor authoritarianism and brutality regime viewed the civil society with suspicion and as the agent of the opposition. The civil society was brutally attacked forcing many to exile, hence affected the role of civil society in Liberia. Nonetheless, the civil society was involved in the negotiations of the Accra CPA which resulted in them getting 18 seats in the National Transitional Legislative Assembly and shared among special interest groups. Limited CSOs in Liberia had always been active advocacy security sector for reasons considered to be a dangerous task but the Liberian National Law Enforcement Association (LINLEA) is the only one that had been persistent since the 1990s, and after the CPA it was at

the forefront advocacy of SSR. LINLEA also advocates for professionalism and respect of human rights within the police force as well as representing former and serving police officers (Loden, 2007:302).

4.8. Liberia Parliament/ Civilian Security Sector Oversight

The legislature is an essential engine of democracy and good governance being for stable and robust democracies or countries emerging from conflicts. The ability of the government to lead Parliamentary oversights functions is a real direct gesture of promoting fundamental democratic norms of checks and balances and separation of powers. Thus, the need for the Legislature to preside over the oversights of security sector reform is vital for security governance Ebo, (2005:25). The Liberia 2005 elections brought in 75% percent new and fresh legislators, and legislature capacity building consortium was established to primarily support the Committees on Security and Defence from both upper and lower chambers. The consortium was to offer a need-based support in the areas of research, working sessions, experience sharing as it was working with the Conflict Security and Development Group, African Security Sector Network, the Geneva Centre for Democratic Control of the Armed Forces, the Centre for Democracy and Development to mention among others. The Liberian legislators learned civilian democratic oversight during the consortium and how to make a security sector accountable. A significant milestone was the designing of the 2008 National Defense Act by the legislators that path way for the 2011 National Security and Intelligence Act (Bryden and Chappuis, 2015:67).

4.9. Conclusion.

Liberian had been merged in series of violent conflicts for an extended period which devastated the whole as a state and the entire civil population. All the armed forces that were involved in

the war committed sexual and gender based violence and other dehumanising forms of violations, humiliation, and abuses. Therefore, resuscitating a viable security sector especially the military characterised by a lack of discipline, unprofessionalism, low morale, rampant corruption, and poorly equipped amidst chaos is very challenging. The Liberia security sector reform program under the auspice post-conflict reconstruction process through the help of international community and the Liberian government political will since the CPA was signed. It played a significant role rebuild the Liberian army, trained new Liberian National Police, with the ability to protect and secure its national frontiers, the civilians and the safeguard the Constitution of Liberia.

The SSR made a scale of the program that among to success, the period of about 10-13 years is too short to reconstruct security governance which has a history shaped by warlords and mercenaries. But it's noticeable to see Liberal SSR progress in the security management as the legislature could make a significant milestone in designing of the 2008 National Defence Act that path way for the 2011 National Security and Intelligence Act.

However, this research also acknowledges the fact that the internationally led post-conflict SSR in Liberia fall short of the holistic view of comprehensive SSR of '1) Establishment of efficient governance, accountability and oversight compositions in the security system; 2). Improved delivery of safety and legal services; 3). Development of civic leadership and ownership of the reform process; 4). Sustainability of justice and security service delivery'. The SSR program in Liberia remains not locally owned, Liberia's legal framework was inconsistency and the missing pieces in for national security, the executive overshadows the role judiciary, and the voice of the civil society voices remain limited.

Nevertheless, it's worth mentioning that there are reasons to be optimistic about the direction Liberia is moving towards reforming the security sector. One great optimising is that the guns are silent now, the country is preparing for the 2017 presidential and legislative elections. Security Council also has decided to reduce the UNMIL Mission's military personnel as a gesture of peace and stability exist in Liberia.

CHAPTER FIVE

SIERRA LEONE SECURITY SECTOR REFORM

5.1. Security Sector Reform background in Sierra Leone

The Sierra Leone government adopted a Security Sector Reforms as a national reform agenda since in March 1996 after the country had experienced and continued to experience violent conflict and state collapse. Alhaji Ahmad Tejan Kabbah was in 1996 democratically elected as president of Sierra Leone, and his government inherited security system merged with legacies of colonialism, corruption, war, and years of political and economic mismanagement. Several Sierra Leone government policies, peace agreements, international actions, and development plan jointly demanded the call for SSR to be given priority for peace and stability to be realized in the post-conflict Sierra Leone. The UK considerable support to Sierra Leone went as far as rebuilding where much emphasis was given to reform the security system which was not the only prerequisite but the very foundation of state stability and reconstruction. The UK also provided support to overhaul the Sierra Leone armed forces that had executed two coups in the 1990s. Similarly, there was a massive help for the reform and restructuring of the police forces to re-establish the SLP. (Albrecht, 2010:14; Gbla, 2006:81).

5.2. Sierra Leone Armed Forces Transformation and restructuring

Gbla, (2006:82) asserted that the Armed Forces of Sierra Leone (AFRSL) in the 1990's was characteristic by a lack of discipline, unprofessionalism, low morale, rampant corruption, soldiers were badly trained, and poorly equipped as well as undesirable civil–military relations. Thus, the Armed Forces of Sierra Leone (AFRSL) requires radical reform and restructuring as it had gone to the extent of having the inability to provide to the nation and her citizens. And according to (Malan et al., 2003:89-90) security means the ability by national Armed Forces to

secure the civilians lives from imminent small and large-scale threats of violence. Also, the capacity of a state in restoring and maintain territorial integrity, a tasked in which the Armed Forces of Sierra Leone (AFRSL) had failed to do due to the protracted violent conflict.

The Lome' Agreement that articulated the Sierra Leone's SSR program and demanded the restructuring and reform of the Armed Forces. The program aimed to rebuild new national armed force that is exclusively loyal to the state of Sierra Leone, and these soldiers ought to be willing to carry out their constitutional mandate. The reform and restructuring program was to rebuild professionalism in the Armed Forces of Sierra Leone which is accountable to the civilians, respect human rights, have transparent financial management procedures, and have the sense of democratic values. These would create public confidence in the Armed Forces that had lost the citizens confidence. Therefore, the Armed Forces restructuring and reform can be achieved through increasing the professionalism, transparent recruitment process, adequate skills training, improve living conditions by the provision of accommodation and decent salary pay (Onoma, 2014:145; Gbla, 2006:83).

As a transformation and restructuring of the Sierra Leone Armed Forces, (Malan et al., 2003:89-90) noted the generous support of the United Kingdom to reform the Sierra Leone Armed Forces that was carried out by DFID. The program aimed at equipping, training and advising Sierra Leone government forces. The SSR reform agenda through the support of the United Kingdom helped the establishment of high Ministry of Defence in Sierra Leonean with the ability to; "formulate, implement, monitor and evaluate the Republic Sierra Leone Armed Forces strategic defense policy for effectiveness and fostered within a democratic governance framework." Gbla, (2006:84). From the year 1999, the United Kingdom did a series of training programs under the International Military Advisory and Training Team (IMATT). Short-term

training teams of about 12-week training offered to the Republic of Sierra Leone Armed Forces (RSLAF). The basic training was expected to train about 12,500 soldiers with specialized training in the areas of command and control, logistics, communications, among others.

Conceivably the SSR program in Sierra Leonean was conceived to be one of the exceptional success in the history of SSR concept as peace-building and conflict prevention program in the post-conflict African countries. Unlike in the past, the Sierra Leonean Armed forces restored existing military-civilian working relationship, re-established the public confidence, trained, equipped, and professionalized soldiers who are responsible for the security of civilians lives from threats of violence, and the ability the National Armed Forces to grantee the territorial integrity of the country. Consequently, the supplement of the transformation and restructuring of the Sierra Leone Armed Forces foster peace and security in Sierra Leone which bolsters political, social, economic and development prosperity as components of peace-building, stability, and reconstruction of post-conflict countries processes.

5.3 Sierra Leone Police Reform

The Sierra Leone Police Force (SLP) institution for an extended period characterized by rampant corruption, inefficiency, poor service conditions, politicisation, inadequate infrastructure, and equipment. Meaning the Sierra Leone police force for long needed reform and restructuring to respond to post-conflict security challenges adequately. The Sierra Leone 1964 Police Act narrowly defined the role of the police to only 'preservation of law and order, the detection of crime and apprehension of offenders, Law enforcement regulations, and protection of property.' The police force legal framework that it operates under and the limited resources made it difficult to address to post-war security challenges in an efficient and accountable manner. Thus, reform was imminent (Gbla, 2007:25-27; 2006:86-87).

After the 1996 general democratic elections that brought in President Kabbah to power, the then government and its international partners (DFID and Foreign and Commonwealth Office) thought of the dire need for the police force reform and restructuring program. Therefore, the plan broadly focused on areas of redefining the Sierra Leone Police force (SLP's) role, mechanisms for oversight, the police composition and training, conditions of service and budget allocation. According to (Albrecht, 2010:20), the government political good will to the police reform and restructuring was a gesture by the leadership of the then-President Kabbah who requested for the appointment retired UK police officer Keith Biddle as Inspector-General of Police. The government also invited a seven-member Commonwealth policy development task force in 1998 to coordinate the program. The Task Force was asked to 'devise a working framework plan for police force rebuilding, advise on policy practice, respect for human rights, training, and recruitment.' Gbla, (2007:25-27; 2006:86-87).

Gbla, (2007:25-27; 2006:86-87) asserted that the Sierra Leone government in 1998 released the Police Charter which outlines the role of the police force concerning the government and people. And a strong emphasis on professionalism, equal opportunity, and local needs was policing. In ensuring the standard of the police force, the charter made clear mission statement which encompasses the components professionalism, respect for human rights and freedoms, winning public confidence, impartiality, honesty, responding to local needs, free from corruption, reliable and accountable police services among others (Krogstad, 2012:270-271).

Therefore, the success of the Sierra Leone Police force reform and restructuring program under the context of Security Sector Reform that groomed police officers to take the leadership position as soon as the British departed. These including the appointment of women to senior police position had enabled the Sierra Leone local security forces assumed the security

responsibility of the entire country in 2005 even after the withdrawal of the UNAMSIL military force in December 2005. (Ginifer, 2006:802) Emphasised that the reform and restructuring program managed to put oversight mechanisms in places like the highest police body that have got the power to provide civilian oversight of policing in Sierra Leone and the police council. The provision of efficient and accountable security by the Sierra Leone Police force gain them public confidence. Henceforth, the Police force reform and restructuring success reinforce the Rule of Law which is a crucial component in the post-war reconstruction and state building processes.

5.4 The Sierra Leone Law or Judiciary Reform

The Sierra Leone judiciary system was by far regarded as unprofessional, corrupt, and inefficient. Thus, Gbla, (2007:88; 2006:28) recognized that effective justice system is very crucial in promoting the principles of good governance. The Sierra Leone SSR program paid maxima attention to improving the robust, vigorous and efficient judiciary system. The Sierra Leone government and the UK DFID-fund co-operated to the Law Reform Programme which aimed to; improve the ability, capacity and working effectiveness of the judiciary, including higher courts and local courts applying customary law. Reform of the legal code to better reflect contemporary needs and the presentation of this redrafted legislation to Parliament through the Ministry of Justice; and Training of all levels of legal personnel, including High Court judges, Albrecht, (2010:69).

The UK DFID-fund for the JSDP was initiated to help the government in improving access to affordable justice, provide support for the rule of law, contribute to prevent further conflict and enhance safety and security, mainly the marginalized, poor, and the vulnerable. And the law Development program had provided infrastructure improvement and training for the Judiciary,

although huge problems in the justice's sector elements like (prisons, probation, legal reform, non-state justice, and legal advice) had not benefited from the development assistance, Albrecht and Jackson, (2009:130-132).

5.5. The Sierra Leone Security Sector Parliament/ Civilian Oversight

The Sierra Leone security sector had no sufficient legislative/civilian oversight control Ginifer, (2006:802). The Sierra Leone Legislative scrutiny maintained to be weak due to lack of parliamentarian's administrative staffs with the security sector expertise, and in some instance, opinion proves that parliamentarians do not sincerely acknowledge their role in oversight sufficiently. Even though the 1991 Constitution instituted such institutions tasked with the obligations and powers to supervise the state's security troops. Thus, these institutions included; 'the Committee on Presidential Affairs and Defence responsible for national security and defense, the Transparency Committee that deals with matters of dishonesty/corruption as well as abuse of public office. Committee for Internal Affairs and Local Government tasked with the responsibilities to monitors the police and the prison regime.' Therefore, Gbla, (2006:87-88) asserted that DFID made an initiative to support the legislative capacity-building project to guarantee that efforts to improve monitoring capacity role by parliament over the security sector.

5.6. Conclusion

In conclusion, the success of the Sierra Leone SSR program in reforming the RSLAF and SLP led to the effectiveness and efficiency of the Sierra Leone Armed forces. Common knowledge detects that post-war reconstruction processes cut across political, economic/developmental and security dimension. But, out of these three dimensions, the security dimension plays a

fundamental role in enabling a secure environment for the political, economic/developmental. Thus, security dimension is given an urgent priority.

Even though the Sierra Leone SSR program criticized for being more concerned with 'hard' security, the program had managed to paid maxima attention to improving the robust, vigorous and efficient judiciary system. And this was evident by the fact that the Sierra Leone government and the UK DFID-fund collaborated to the Law Reform Programme which aimed to; improve the ability, capacity and working effectiveness of the judiciary, including higher courts and local courts applying customary law. Besides that, the Sierra Leone SSR program could develop the Parliamentary and civilian oversight mechanism tasked with the responsibilities and powers to oversee the state's security forces.

The success of the Sierra Leone SSR proves that Security sector reform is a crucial component in the post-war reconstruction processes that reinforced peace building and stability in the state-building and reconstruction processes. The Sierra Leone SSR program had earned and restored the public confidence in the security forces because SLP had been strengthened with the necessary resource to improve their efficiency in containing riots, civil unrest, domestic violence and economic crimes. The success of the Sierra Leone SSR proves that Security sector reform is a crucial component in the post-war reconstruction processes that enhanced peace building and stability in the state-building and reconstruction processes. The Sierra Leone SSR program had earned and restored the public confidence in the security forces because SLP had been strengthened with the necessary resource to improve their efficiency in containing riots, civil unrest, domestic violence and economic crimes. The evidence that there had existed no resurgence of violent conflict in Sierra Leone indicates that the success of SSR reinforces peacebuilding and stability.

CHAPTER SIX

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

6.1. Summary

The primary objective of the research was to examine how the success of Security sector reform reinforce peace building and stability in the state building and reconstruction processes of post-war African countries with a keen interest in Sierra Leone and Liberia. The study found that both Sierra Leone and Liberia have similar histories as ex-slave's destinations from America and people British Navy rescued from the slave's ships en route to America. The settlers in both territories were known as Amerio-Liberians and Krio, they formed the local ruling elites in the respective states, and they have suffered from intimately protracted civil wars after their independence.

The study indicated that both countries emerged from protracted violent conflict (civil war), and their post-war period characterized by post-conflict reconstruction through international community intervention in rebuilding the state and in some cases building various state institutions from scratch. For example, Britain's Department for International Development (DFID), the Ministry of Defence (MOD) and the US State Department invested significant effort and resources in reforming the Armed Forces of Liberia (AFL), LNP, and the then Armed Forces of the Republic of Sierra Leone (AFRSL) including the police forces. And security sector reform was one the post-conflict reconstruction method employed in both countries which have enhanced the restoration of public safety because of the SSR success in Sierra Leone and Liberia. However, the researcher used the term 'Success' carefully, and the phrase does not indicate overall achievement of the total holistic goal of SSR, rather, an indication of the significant and sustained recovery of the security conditions in Africa post-war countries.

The study acknowledged the limited functional oversight mechanisms, and a failure to involve other actors beyond the executive arm of government in the governance of the security sector. Security sector reform in both countries disputed over much focused on the 'hard security' other than comprehensive reforms in the security system.

6.2. Conclusion

Sierra Leone and Liberia were compounded in series of violent conflicts for an extended period that devastated the state institutions and the entire civil population. Their armed forces were involved in dehumanizing, humiliation, and abuses as they committed systematic human rights violations like sexual and gender based violence. Therefore, resuscitating a viable security sector especially the military forces characterized by a lack of discipline, unprofessionalism, low morale, rampant corruption, and poorly equipped amidst chaos would be extremely essential. The reform of the security sector aimed to improve the structure, professionalism, and operational ability of the security agencies to be able to work in a democratic framework with an elected civilian government. The reform of the military, police, prisons authority, intelligence agencies, and judicial structures noted as wider part security sector reform which is central to post-conflict reconstruction not only in Sierra Leone and Liberia but also in many African countries that emerged from violent conflict.

The research found that both countries implementation of the security reform program through the help of international donor partners registered significant success in rebuilding all the security agencies that are responsible for the provision of safety, with the ability to protect and secure their national frontiers, the civilians, and the safeguard their Constitutions. The considerable success of the SSR in both countries demonstrates that Security sector reform is a central component in the post-war reconstruction processes that enhanced peace building and

stability in the state-building and reconstruction processes. The SSR program had earned and restored the public confidence in the security forces because SSR had strengthened all the security agencies that are responsible for the provision of safety with the necessary resource to improve their efficiency in containing riots, civil unrest, domestic violence and economic crimes. The proof that there had existed no resurgence of violent conflict in Sierra Leone and Liberia indicated the fact that success of SSR reinforces peacebuilding and stability.

Both states operationalized the SSR principles and had considerable success in implementing the SSR program as they have established a self-sustaining security system in their countries.

Thus, successful implementation of SSR through the support of international community and individual donor nations in the post-conflict African countries reinforced the theory of peacebuilding and stability because creating a secure environment for the civilian's lives make the country to have 'freedom from want' and 'freedom from fear.'

However, this research has acknowledged the fact that the internationally led post-conflict SSR in Sierra Leone and Liberia fall short of the holistic view of comprehensive SSR of '1) Establishment of efficient governance, accountability and oversight compositions in the security system; 2). Improved delivery of safety and legal services; 3). Development of civic leadership and ownership of the reform process; 4). Sustainability of justice and security service delivery'. The SSR program in Liberia remains not only locally owned, but Liberia's legal framework was also inconsistency and the missing pieces in for national security, the executive overshadows the role judiciary, and the voice of the civil society voices remain limited.

Even though the Sierra Leone and Liberia SSR program were criticized for being more concerned with 'hard' security, the program had managed to paid maxima attention to

improving the robust, vigorous and efficient judiciary system in Sierra Leone. And this was evident by the fact that the Sierra Leone government and the UK DFID-fund collaborated to the Law Reform Programme which aimed to; improve the ability, capacity and working effectiveness of the judiciary, including higher courts and local courts applying customary law. Also in Liberia security oversight management made significant milestone as the legislature designed the 2008 National Defence Act that path way for the 2011 National Security and Intelligence Act.

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